

Halogenomercuriphenols.

BY JOHN FERNAND CAIUS AND JAL HIRJI WADIA.

Halogenomercuriphenols are derivatives of benzene characterized by the presence of a nuclear hydroxyl, and by the mercury being linked to a nuclear carbon atom through one valency and to an halogen atom through the other. They are represented by the following types: -

Desesquelle (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1894, **11**, 263) prepared *p*-chloromercuriphenol by the interaction of potassium phenolate and mercuric chloride. Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2155; 1899, **32**, 761) obtained the three chloromercuriphenols by the action of a saturated solution of sodium chloride on the hot filtrate from the interaction of mercuric oxide, glacial acetic acid, and phenol, in hot aqueous solution. Whitmore and Middleton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 622) prepared the two monochloromercuriphenols by adding a hot solution of sodium chloride to a boiling aqueous solution of the products obtained by heating phenol and mercuric acetate on the steam-bath. Whitmore and Hanson ("Organic Syntheses," 1925, IV, p. 13) obtained *o*-chloromercuriphenol by a method which does not essentially differ from that adopted by Whitmore and Middleton (*loc. cit.*).

By modifying the methods used by those authors we have succeeded in elaborating a general mode of preparation which applies not only to the chloromercuri-compounds, but also to the bromo-, iodo-, and fluoro-mercuri-derivatives. The more salient points are that the mono-derivatives are precipitated in the cold, and that the di-derivatives are obtained from pure crystallised diacetoxymercuriphenol.

The reactions involved are (1) in the case of the monohalogeno-mercuriphenols,

and (2) in the case of the dihalogenomercuriphenols,

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Mercuric Acetate.—One kg. of mercuric chloride is added gradually to 580 c.c. of a saturated solution of sodium chloride kept at 95-96°. As soon as the whole has gone into solution, 160 c.c. of a 50 per cent. solution of sodium hydroxide are slowly poured into it with constant stirring. The precipitate is allowed to settle and then the supernatant liquid is siphoned off. The precipitate is washed six or seven times with large amounts of distilled water and freed from sodium hydroxide and sodium chloride. The moist mercuric oxide is dissolved by gradual addition of glacial acetic acid, and the solution kept in the cold chamber at 4-5°. The crystals of mercuric acetate are removed and dried as long as the mother-liquor keeps colourless. Yield almost theoretical.

In this method of preparation advantage is taken (1) of the great solubility of mercuric chloride in a saturated aqueous solution of sodium chloride, and (2) of the readiness with which moist mercuric oxide dissolves in acetic acid.

Preparation of the Acetoxymmercuriphenols.—100 Gm. of solid phenol are added to 200 gm. of mercuric acetate in 1200 c.c. of water and a few drops of glacial acetic acid. On stirring the substances dissolve and a colourless solution is obtained. Within an hour the insoluble diacetoxymmercuriphenol is formed and can be separated by filtration.

(1) The *filtrate* (A) contains a mixture of the soluble *o*- and *p*-acetoxymmercuriphenols and is used directly in the preparation of the monohalogenomercuri-compounds.

(2) The *precipitate* on the filter is washed with distilled water (B) at room temperature until (1) the washings give no precipitate or turbidity on addition of an aqueous saturated solution of sodium

chloride—absence of the monoacetoxymcuriphenols, and (2) the precipitate gives no pink colouration with sodium nitrite moistened with a few drops of water—absence of *o*-acetoxymcuriphenol.

Diacetoxymcuriphenol crystallises from 30 per cent. acetic acid in shining plates. Powder gritty white, m.p. 216°. Yield, 102 gm.

Preparation of the Dihalogenomcuriphenols.—Diacetoxymcuriphenol (61 g.) is dissolved in a solution (75 c.c. of a 6·5 per cent.) of sodium hydroxide, filtered through hard ammoniated filter paper. It is shaken with an excess of a saturated solution of the sodium halide, and then treated with acetic acid gradually until the liquid is distinctly acid to litmus. It is filtered, washed free of sodium halide, sodium acetate, or acetic acid, and dried over sulphuric acid in *vacuo*.

Difluoromcuriphenol.—White, soft powder melting at 197·5–198°. Yield, 2·5 gm.. (Found: Hg, 76·16. $C_6H_4OHg_2F_2$ requires Hg, 76·82 per cent.).

Dichloromcuriphenol.—White, slightly gritty powder, unaffected by light or moisture, decomposing at 278°. Yield, 35 gm. (Found: Hg, 70·92. Calc. Hg, 71·12 per cent.).

Dibromomcuriphenol.—White, rough powder, unaffected by light or moisture, turning greyish at 230°. Yield, 5 gm. (Found: Hg, 60·94. $C_6H_4OHg_2Br_2$ requires Hg, 61·44 per cent.).

Di-iodomcuriphenol.—Yellowish, slightly rough powder, affected by light and moisture with slow formation of mercuric iodide, decomposing at 142°. Yield, 12 gm. (Found: Hg, 53·19. $C_6H_4OHg_2I_2$ requires Hg, 53·70 per cent.).

Preparation of the Monohalogenomcuriphenols.—The filtrate (A) and the washings (B) from the preparation of the acetoxymcuriphenols are treated in the cold with an aqueous solution of the sodium halide—saturated in the case of the chloride and the fluoride, 1: 10 for the bromide, 1: 100 for the iodide—as long as a precipitate forms. This precipitate is a mixture of *ortho*- and *para*-halogenomcuriphenols together with a small amount of dihalogenomcuriphenol.

1. Boiling water removes the *ortho*-compound which crystallises on cooling. The mother-liquor is then concentrated, and crystals are collected as long as they separate pure.

o-Fluoromcuriphenol.—Very small, shining needles; light drab gritty powder melting at 192·5°. Yield, 2·5 gm. (Found: Hg, 63·71. C_6H_5OHgF requires Hg, 64·16 per cent.).

o-Chloromercuriphenol.—Long thick needles ; white rough powder melting at 146-146·5°. Yield, 61·2 gm. (Found: Hg, 60·72. Calc. Hg, 60·95 per cent.).

o-Bromomercuriphenol.—Short needles in rosettes ; white soft powder melting at 121·5^p—122°. Yield, 8·9 gm. (Found: Hg, 53·25. C_6H_5OHgBr requires Hg, 53·72 per cent.).

o-Iodomercuriphenol.—Long shining silky needles ; white, soft powder melting at 106·5°. Yield, 3 gm. (Found: Hg, 47·09. C_6H_5OHgI requires Hg, 47·93 per cent.).

2. The *para*-compound is extracted with boiling absolute alcohol from which it crystallises on standing.

p-Fluoromercuriphenol does not crystallise ; white, soft powder melting at 204°. Yield, 3 gm. (Found: Hg, 63·36. C_6H_5OHgF requires Hg, 64·16 per cent.).

p-Chloromercuriphenol.—Large plates ; white rough powder melting at 216°. Yield, 22 gm. (Found: Hg, 60·32. Calc. Hg, 60·95 per cent.).

p-Bromomercuriphenol.—Large glistening flakes ; white, gritty powder changing colour at 185°, without melting. Yield, 8·6 gm. (Found: Hg, 53·35. C_6H_5OHgBr requires Hg, 53·72 per cent.).

p-Iodomercuriphenol.—Large shining flakes ; white, slightly rough powder turning golden yellow at 180° without melting. Yield, 56·5 gm. (Found: Hg, 47·58. C_6H_5OHgI requires Hg, 47·93 per cent.).